

Use of metal co-ordination compounds as antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : Mixed ligand transition metal complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with dibasic oxalic acid as primary ligand and benzoyl hydrazine as secondary ligand have been synthesized. Their conventional physical and chemical analyses have been done. On the basis of physico-chemical analysis and spectral studies metal complexes may be formulated as [M(OA)(BH)₂], where M stands for bivalent metal ion, OA for oxalate ion and BH for benzoyl hydrazine. The complexes are quite stable coloured solid but sparingly soluble in water. Magnetic moment values and spectral studies reveal that an octahedral geometry has been assigned to all the prepared complexes. The synthesized metal complexes were screened for *in vitro* antifungal activity against the multi drug resistant fungal pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici* causing disease in vegetable crops. *In vitro* antifungal screening indicates that the complexes show enhanced antifungal activities against the fungal strains compared with parental compounds.

Keywords : Mixed ligand, transition metal complexes, *in vitro* antifungal screening, *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*.

Introduction

Throughout history, there has been a continual battle between humans and the micro-organisms that cause infection and disease not only in humans but also in plants, producing vegetables and fruits. In recent years, efforts have been devoted to the synthesis and characterization of metal-based drugs¹. Mixed ligand transition metal complexes represent a novel group of antibacterial and antifungal agents with potential applications for the control of bacterial and fungal infections². Mixed ligand transition metal complexes have powerful antimicrobial activities. Enormous work and research have been done so far for improving and developing new transition metal complexes. Transition metals exhibit different oxidation states and can interact with a number of negatively charged molecules. During the past decades, much attention has been given to the synthesis of new metal complexes and the evaluation of these agents for antimicrobial activity³⁻⁵. Still, the need for new transition metal complexes is there, for medical and other beneficial applications. The antifungal activity of mixed ligand transition metal complexes against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici* responsible for wilt disease in tomato crop is very scanty. It is a fact

that the demand for new and better complexes has never ended, in fact it has been increasing to a greater degree and with bigger dimensions than even before, especially in recent times.

The nature of co-ordination complex depends on the metal ion, the structure and nature of ligand and the metal-ligand interaction. The complexation of metal ions with ligands not only affects their physical characteristics, but also their chemical activity. Complexation increases the biological activity of compounds. As a part of our ongoing work⁶ on mixed ligand transition metal complexes, the present study communicates the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with oxalic acid and benzoyl hydrazine as ligands. Their antifungal activities investigated to perform primary selection of these complexes as the therapeutic agent.

Results and discussion

Elemental analysis data, magnetic moment and molar conductivities of different complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are coloured solid which are quite stable at room temperature. The complexes were found

Table 1. Characterization data of mixed ligand metal complexes

Sr. No.	Complex	Colour	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)				μ_{eff} (BM)	Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N	Metal		
1.	Mn(OA)(BH) ₂	Chocolate brown	46.28 (46.34)	3.88 (3.92)	13.49 (13.56)	13.23 (13.48)	5.94	17.92
2.	Co(OA)(BH) ₂	Dark pink	45.84 (45.92)	3.85 (3.71)	13.36 (13.52)	14.06 (14.21)	4.94	20.11
3.	Ni(OA)(BH) ₂	Parrot green	45.77 (45.98)	3.84 (3.64)	13.34 (13.42)	13.98 (14.20)	3.01	23.46
4.	Cu(OA)(BH) ₂	Dark violet	45.34 (45.52)	3.80 (3.98)	13.22 (13.32)	14.99 (15.12)	1.79	28.01
5.	Zn(PA)(BH) ₂	Greenish white	45.14 (44.98)	3.79 (3.6)	13.16 (12.94)	15.36 (15.62)	–	26.08

stable up to 250 °C. But above this they dissociate. These complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but completely soluble in DMSO and DMF. However the complexes are very sparingly soluble in water. Conductivity data also confirm this nature. The purity of complexes was checked by TLC. On the basis of elemental analysis/characterization data the complexes are formulated as [M(OA)(BH)₂], where M stands for bivalent metal ion, OA for oxalate ion and BH for benzoyl hydrazine.

Magnetic properties :

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate paramagnetic nature for Mn, Co, Ni and Cu complexes. The magnetic moment observed for Mn^{II} complex is 5.94 BM which is consistent with the octahedral geometry of the complex⁷. The six co-ordinate Co^{II} complex exhibit magnetic moment of 4.94 BM suggesting octahedral geometry for Co^{II} complex⁸. Ni^{II} complex showed magnetic moment 3.01 BM slightly higher than the spin only value, indicating an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion⁹. The observed magnetic moments for Cu^{II} complex is 1.79 BM suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry around Cu^{II}¹⁰. The Zn^{II} complex was found to be diamagnetic, while all other complexes were para-

magnetic with magnetic moment values close to the spin only values¹¹.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of Mn^{II} mixed ligand complexes showed ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions at 15010, 18200 and 24510 cm^{-1} respectively which may be attributed to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ respectively. The ν_2/ν_1 value is in accordance with Mn^{II} octahedral complexes¹². In Co^{II} complexes the bands observed at 9020, 18300 and 20510 cm^{-1} may be due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ charge transfer transitions respectively in an octahedral field¹³. Ni^{II} complex showed three transitions at 9875, 16300 and 25300 cm^{-1} as ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The ν_2/ν_1 value for the present compound is in the usual range (1.60–1.82) reported for majority of octahedral Ni^{II} complexes^{13,14}. Ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, B , β and β° have been calculated from the electronic spectra of the complexes and are given in Table 2. These data are in accordance with the octahedral/distorted octahedral geometry of complexes as reported earlier. The copper(II) complex showed one broad band at 13445 cm^{-1} .

Table 2. Electronic spectra and ligand field parameters

Sr. No.	Complex	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	$10 Dq$ (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	β°	ν_2/ν_1
1.	Mn(OA)(BH) ₂	15010	18200	24510	14901.67	626.11	0.728	27.2	1.21
2.	Co(OA)(BH) ₂	9020	18300	20510	9280	783.33	0.806	19.4	2.03
3.	Ni(OA)(BH) ₂	9875	16300	25300	9875	798.33	0.775	22.5	1.65
4.	Cu(OA)(BH) ₂	1344 band maxima	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Which may be due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition showing distorted octahedral geometry^{11,12,15}.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectroscopy is a powerful and useful unambiguous tool of structural determination for complexes of transition metals. A large number of co-ordination compounds are being investigated using infrared methods. When a ligand is co-ordinated to the metal ion, the metal atom or ion is introduced in to the ligands vibrating system and the infrared spectrum of the co-ordinated ligand will thus be different from that of the free ligand. In the present investigation the infrared spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of bivalent '3d' transition metal ions with oxalic acid and benzoyl hydrazine have been recorded. The association of carboxylic acid is well known to take place through -COOH groups. It is therefore expected that mainly -OH and -C=O bonds of the monomeric molecules would be affected. In case of dimeric molecules OH frequencies lies between 2500–300 cm^{-1} in the form of a broad absorption band. The asymmetric carbonyl stretching frequency of carboxylic acid has been noted at 1690–1710 cm^{-1} . It is well known that when carboxylate is formed that characteristic carbonyl absorption is replaced by two bands in the region 1500–1600 cm^{-1} and 1300–1420 cm^{-1} corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of carboxylate group. The infrared spectra of oxalate complexes have been studied. The free oxalate group belongs to D_{2h} symmetry and shows new ν_{as} (C=O) and ν_s (C=O) modes at 1640 and 1335 cm^{-1} respectively. In chelated oxalato

complexes the asymmetric and symmetric C=O vibrations become IR active. The infrared frequencies associated with oxalato group in the complexes reported here are in good agreement with these normally associated with the bidentate chelating oxalato group. The carboxylate ion in all the complexes reported here co-ordinates to the metal ion as bidentate ligands via both the carboxylate groups. OH stretching absorption appearing at 3175–3030 cm^{-1} in oxalic acid, disappears in its salts in the complexes of metal oxalate with benzoyl hydrazine. The amide-1 band occurring at 1650 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of benzoyl hydrazine disappears and new band appears at about 1680 cm^{-1} , suggesting the shifting of amide-1 band on complexation. It also indicates the involvement of oxygen atom of -COOH and nitrogen atom of -NH₂ groups in co-ordination. The bands observed at about 1700, 1400, 1365 and 1300 cm^{-1} were not found in the spectra of benzoyl hydrazine, therefore identified as ν_{as} (C=O) and ν_s (C=O). The evidence for nitrogen co-ordination is available from the appearance of new bands of low energy vibrational spectra. The ν (M-N) vibrations in the complexes have been assigned on a comparison of IR bands free ligands and the metal complexes. The bands observed in the region 450–420 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ν (M-N) whereas the bands observed in the region 565–520 cm^{-1} have been assigned to ν (M-O)^{16–23} (Table 3).

Electron paramagnetic resonance study :

The X-band EPR spectrum of the manganese(II) complex observed at room temperature is shown in Fig. 1 has six hyperfine lines centered around *g*-value 2.015, which

Table 3. Important IR spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of mixed ligand complexes

Sr. No.	Complex	ν (N-H) or ν (NH ₂)	ν_{as} (C=O) + NH ₂ bonding	ν_s (C=O)	ν (M-O)	ν (M-N)
1.	Mn(OA)(BH) ₂	3250s br, 3350s br	1680m	1465s, 1410s	565m	428w
2.	Co(OA)(BH) ₂	3240s br	1695s	1385m, 1350s	520m	430m
3.	Ni(OA)(BH) ₂	3355m br, 3350s br	1700m, 1645m	1470m	550m	422w
4.	Cu(OA)(BH) ₂	3375m br	1670s	1365m, 1300s	545m	435m
5.	Zn(OA)(BH) ₂	3340m br	1710m	1410s, 1398m	525m	430m, 450w

Fig. 1. Powder X-band EPR spectrum of Mn^{II} at room temperature (300 K).

was characteristic of octahedral site symmetry of manganese(II) complex. These EPR parameters indicates that this manganese(II) species has octahedral co-ordination, consistent with an extra-framework position²⁴. In the literature g -value for the hyperfine splitting is indicative of the nature of the bonding. If the g -value shows a negative shift with respect to the free electron value (2.0023) then the bonding is considered as ionic and conversely, if the shift is positive then the bonding may be more covalent. In the present case, the g -value shows positive shift, indicative of covalent bonding between manganese(II) and ligand.

The EPR spectrum of copper(II) complex provides information of importance in studying the metal ion environment. The X-band EPR spectrum of the copper(II) at room temperature exhibit an isotropic signal, without any hyperfine splitting (Fig. 2). The room temperature spectra of powdered sample was recorded at 9450 MHz both parallel and perpendicular features of copper are resolved in the spectra, which are characteristic of axial symmetry. The $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} component for the complex were calculated as 2.22 and 2.04. The g -value of the copper(II) complex is found to be 2.1095, reported for a number of distorted copper(II) complexes. Moreover, the observed g -value is less than 2.3, suggesting a covalent nature of metal-ligand bonds in the complex^{25,26}. The lines of this type are observed usually due to either to the intermo-

Fig. 2. Powder X-band EPR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex at room temperature (300 K).

lecular spin exchange, which may broaden the lines, or to the occupancy of the unpaired electron in the degenerate orbitals. The nature and the pattern of the EPR spectra suggest an almost octahedral environment around the copper(II) complex.

Antimicrobial activity :

The *in vitro* antifungal activity on the radial growth of the pathogen was evaluated by food poison technique against the fungus *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*. The diseased root pieces of tomato plant were taken for *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici* and the specimen were collected from IIVR, Varanasi. The surface was sterilized with mercuric chloride (0.1%) for 30 s, rinsed thrice with sterile water, blotted dry and isolated on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium at 25 ± 1 °C for seven days. Food poison technique was applied to test different concentrations i.e. 100, 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000 ppm for each metal complex. After mixing the complex (different concentrations) and solidification of the medium, the pathogen was inoculated in the centre of each petri plate and incubated at 25 ± 1 °C for 5 days. At the end of incubation period the radial colony growth was measured in each treatment. One control treatment was also made to compare the effect. The results of radial growth of the fungus by different complexes at 100, 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000 ppm concentrations have been given in Table 4. The results showed that all the complexes have antifungal activity against the fungus causing wilt disease in tomato. The data showed that out of the five complexes copper complex was more effective against the radial growth of the pathogen at all concentrations. Ni

Table 4. *In vitro* antifungal activity of metal complex against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici* (radial growth in mm)

Sr. No.	Complex	Doses (ppm)					Control	Mean
		100	500	1000	2000	3000		
1.	Mn(OA)(BH) ₂	48.5	45.2	40.5	33.2	26.5	47	40.15
2.	Co(OA)(BH) ₂	50.0	46.2	40.2	36.1	29.2	47	41.45
3.	Ni(OA)(BH) ₂	42.5	38.2	35.5	30.2	28.5	47	36.98
4.	Cu(OA)(BH) ₂	30.5	27.6	20.5	15.2	10.2	47	25.15
5.	Zn(OA)(BH) ₂	46.5	36.2	30.5	30.0	20.0	47	35.03

complex may be placed at second position and Co complex at third position. Mn and Zn complexes showed almost same antifungal activities. However all the complexes are more effective as compared to the ligands²⁷.

The results of *in vitro* studies revealed that at 3000 ppm concentration all the five complexes showed the maximum inhibition in the radial growth of the fungi *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*. Out of these five complexes the radial growth was minimum in the case of copper complex. This clearly indicates that the copper complex may be considered as the best to control the fungal growth out of the five complexes. It binds the protein to grow, resulting the inhibition of growth of pathogen. The antifungal activity of this complex was compared with known drugs prochloraz and bromuconazol. The literature reveals that these two drugs are very effective against the radial growth of *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*²⁸. It was found that at 3000 ppm the radial growth of these two drugs prochloraz and bromuconazol was 10.8 mm and 10.6 mm respectively. Whereas the radial growth of copper complex reported in this study was 10.2 mm. This shows better inhibition than the drugs prochloraz and bromuconazol.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used in the synthesis of transition metal complexes were of analytical grade. Metal salts used in the present study were metal dichlorides. Used oxalic acid was of highest purity. Methanol, ethanol and benzene were further purified by double distillation. Oxalic acid was used as primary ligand and benzoyl hydrazine as secondary ligand. Benzoyl hydrazine was prepared as reported earlier³. Mixed ligand transition metal complexes were prepared as reported by Sharma *et al.*²⁹.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated microanalytically on Elementar Vario EL III elemental analyzer at CDRI, Lucknow. Conductivity measurements were made on ELICO EQ 660 conductivity bridge using DMF as a solvent. Metal contents were estimated by standard methods³⁰. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. The diamagnetic correction of metal-ligand system was calculated using Pascal's constant. The purity of metal complexes was checked by TLC method along with standard ligands. IR spectra in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a Shimadzu FTIR 8201 P C spectrometer where as spectra in the range 4000–250 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infra red spectrophotometer 521 at the Department of Chemistry, IIT, Roorkee. The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a Shimadzu UV 1601 spectrophotometer. The antifungal activities were carried out at IIVR, Varanasi and Microbiological Lab, IFTM University, Moradabad.

Fungicidal screening :

Food poisoning method was found to be effective technique to assess antifungal activity of chemical fungicides against pathogen. Hyphal growth inhibition on the growth medium incorporated with fungicide was determined according to method as reported earlier³¹.

Conclusion

The work described in this paper involved the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of manganese, cobalt, nickel, copper and zinc complexes with dibasic oxalic acid and benzoyl hydrazine ligands. These complexes were characterized by using different physicochemical techniques. The IR spectra revealed that oxalate ion behaves as bidentate chelating ligand co-ordinated to the

metal ion through oxygen atom of -COOH and benzoyl hydrazine ligand co-ordinate through nitrogen atom of -NH₂ group. The magnetic moment and electronic spectra confirm the presence of octahedral geometry of the complexes. The *in vitro* antifungal activity on the radial growth of the fungus refers that the complexes have a significant inhibition efficiency against *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*. Transition metal complexes with bioligands represents a novel group of antimicrobial agents with potential application for the control of fungal infections and used to treat the drug resistant fungal pathogens.

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